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La interacción entre valores socioculturales, comportamiento y bienestar: Rasgos destacados de la inteligencia social

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Resumen. Hoy en día, los estudiantes se ven obligados a navegar por una dinámica social intrincada, exhibiendo una profunda capacidad de comprensión empática y adaptándose rápidamente a diversas demandas situacionales. Su espíritu sociocultural está arraigado en un entramado de normas, tradiciones y sistemas de creencias culturales, que dan forma a sus interacciones y su visión del mundo. Las virtudes y fortalezas del carácter se asocian positivamente con el enfoque de estrategias de afrontamiento entre los estudiantes universitarios, facilitando el crecimiento personal y la adaptación a situaciones desafiantes. Este estudio explora factores clave y rasgos destacados de la inteligencia social entre estudiantes universitarios dentro de un contexto sociocultural. Los valores humanos, vistos como creencias internas y objetivos finales, desempeñan un papel crucial en la configuración del comportamiento y las actitudes. La inteligencia social, vinculada a la satisfacción con la vida y al desempeño profesional, abarca rasgos como la perspectiva, el entusiasmo, el liderazgo y la alegría. Se tomó una muestra representativa de 355 estudiantes de facultad, entre estudiantes de pregrado y maestría. El análisis de datos utilizando SPSS reveló correlaciones estadísticamente significativas entre los rasgos de carácter y la inteligencia social. El estudio enfatiza la importancia de la inteligencia social para navegar en interacciones sociales complejas y lograr el éxito en la sociedad. Se subraya la importancia de la inteligencia social, los rasgos de personalidad y los valores en el fomento de un comportamiento positivo. Al comprender y cultivar estos rasgos, las personas pueden adaptarse mejor a su entorno y promover relaciones sociales armoniosas.

Palabras clave: inteligencia social, valores socioculturales, rasgos de carácter, crecimiento personal, desempeño profesional.

The interplay between sociocultural values, behavior and well-being: salient traits of social intelligence

Abstract. Today, students are forced to navigate intricate social dynamics, exhibiting a deep capacity for empathic understanding and adapting quickly to various situational demands. Their socio-cultural spirit is rooted in a web of cultural norms, traditions, and belief systems, which shape their interactions and worldview. Character virtues and strengths are positively associated with the approach of coping strategies among university students, facilitating personal growth and adaptation to challenging situations. This study explores key factors and salient traits of social intelligence among university students within a sociocultural context. Human values, seen as internal beliefs and end goals, play a crucial role in shaping behavior and attitudes. Social intelligence, linked to life satisfaction and professional performance, encompasses traits such as perspective, enthusiasm, leadership and joy. A representative sample of 355 faculty students was taken, including undergraduate and master's students. Data analysis using SPSS revealed statistically significant correlations between character traits and social intelligence. The study emphasizes the importance of social intelligence in navigating complex social interactions and achieving success in society. The importance of social intelligence, personality traits and values in promoting positive behaviour is underlined. By understanding and cultivating these traits, people can better adapt to their environment and promote harmonious social relationships.

Keywords: social intelligence, sociocultural values, character traits, personal growth, professional performance.

INTRODUCTION

The role of universities in shaping the future of students is multifaceted, extending beyond academic instruction to the development of character strengths and personality traits. This study explores the prevalence of certain character strengths among students and their correlation with social intelligence. The study's methodology and findings provide valuable insights for educational institutions and underscore the importance of nurturing non-academic competencies.

Socio-emotional intelligence is crucial in various aspects of life, including the workplace, academic settings, personal relationships, and self-development. High levels of emotional and social intelligence are linked to positive outcomes such as better mental health, job performance, behavior, and interpersonal relationships (Huerta Cuervo et al., 2022), contributing to a more conducive learning environment and better educational outcomes (Lathifah & Usman, 2019).

In the context of evolving quality education, researchers are investigating diverse methodologies to enhance students' social intelligence. This exploration is conducted with due consideration for individual developmental trajectories and a focus on lifelong learning outcomes. The emphasis is on cultivating students' capacities for effective social interaction and autonomous navigation of interpersonal challenges. The quality of these interpersonal relationships serves as a barometer for the degree to which both students and educators comprehend the social dynamics within educational environments. This multifaceted approach reflects a growing recognition of the importance of social skills in educational development (Wang, 2024).

Human values, representing inner beliefs and ultimate goals, are instrumental in shaping behavior and attitudes. Emotional intelligence is one of the most studied concepts in psychological literature (Vaida & Opre, 2014). Social intelligence, defined by Goleman as the capacity to understand and manage social relationships, is equally key in navigating the educational environment (Goleman, 2010). The educators' role includes understanding students' behavior and encouraging their abilities to social interactions (Yao, 2023).

This study presents compelling research at the intersection of character strengths, psychological well-being, and social intelligence, particularly in academic and professional settings. The paper tackles on a fascinating aspect of how implicit beliefs shape academic outcomes. The idea that implicit intelligence can predict academic performance emphasizes the psychological dimensions of learning. For instance, if a student believes they are "good at math," they are more likely to engage positively with the material, increasing their chances of success. This self-perception doesn't just stop at academics; it interfaces with social intelligence (Meijs, Cillessen, Scholte, Segers, & Spijkerman, 2008). For example, a student excelling in math might gain confidence, leading them to participate more in group projects or discussions. This engagement can enhance their social skills, as they learn to collaborate and communicate effectively with peers (Sik, Cummins, & Job, 2024). Moreover, the early years of education serve as a critical period for shaping these beliefs. Students who receive positive reinforcement may develop a more robust self-concept regarding their intelligence, which can foster resilience in facing academic challenges and nurturing social relationships (Starynska, 2022).

In summary, the interplay between implicit intelligence beliefs and academic performance creates a ripple effect that can enhance social intelligence, illustrating the interconnected nature of cognitive and social development in educational settings. For instance, traits like inquiring intellect and problem-solving, identified as part of social intelligence, are largely shaped by the underlying personality characteristics. It suggests that interpersonal skills and practical intelligence are rooted in broader personality traits rather than just cognitive abilities.

The findings of this study align with the hypothesis, highlighting that personality traits likely encapsulate behaviors that define social intelligence in everyday contexts, demonstrating the interconnectedness of personality and social cognition (Joseph & Lakshmi, 2010).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowledge and love of learning form the successful person (Pokrajčić, 2004) while human values, representing inner beliefs and ultimate goals, are instrumental in shaping behavior and attitudes. Socio-emotional intelligence, an element of humanity's virtue or value, is crucial for several reasons (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). First, it plays a significant role in the emotional well-being of individuals. People with high socio-emotional intelligence are often better equipped to handle stress, build strong relationships, and navigate social complexities. Second, socio-emotional intelligence is essential in the workplace. It contributes to effective performance by enabling individuals to work well in teams, lead others with empathy, and resolve conflicts constructively (Zeidner, Matthews, & Roberts, 2011).

The social intelligence encompasses the aptitude to navigate and adapt to social environments and interactions (Huerta Cuervo et al., 2022), the ability to manage relationships (Goleman, 2010). Socio-emotional competencies are significant factors in the performance and behavior of individu-

als. The review indicates that the concept has been used and interpreted in a diverse range of contexts throughout its historical development.

Other authors explored these concepts and the outcomes of the nuanced interplay between personality traits and social intelligence. The findings suggest that character strengths, such as love and curiosity, can act as intermediaries that translate abstract values into concrete behaviors. For example, fostering an environment where gratitude is expressed can enhance self-transcendence, which can improve interpersonal interactions. The correlation between specific character strengths and psychological well-being indicates that traits like humor and fairness contribute positively to mental health (Darvish, & Taklavi, 2023). This suggests that educational institutions could incorporate activities that enhance these strengths - like teamwork exercises that promote fairness and honest feedback. The discussion emphasizes the importance of developing social intelligence in both personal and professional contexts. Individuals with high social intelligence are portrayed as magnetic and successful, while those with low social intelligence may struggle socially. Practical implications arise here: organizations might implement training programs focusing on improving social intelligence among employees to facilitate better teamwork and reduce conflict. The mention of team coaching aligns with the need for developing social skills in a professional environment. By focusing on social awareness and filtering—two components of social intelligence—organizations can enhance collaboration and communication within teams (Lavy & Benish-Weisman, 2021; Peterson & Seligman, 2004; Quinlan, Swain, & Vella-Brodrick, 2011).

Emotional intelligence is one of the most studied concepts in psychological literature. Emotional intelligence and its relationship with emotional competence offers a critical perspective on their integration in both academic and organizational contexts (Hibbs, 2024). The symbiotic relationship between emotional intelligence and emotional competence is compelling. Vaida & Opre (2014) differentiate between emotional traits, abilities, and competence. Emotional traits are stable characteristics, such as empathy or optimism, that influence how individuals typically respond emotionally. Emotional abilities focus on specific skills or competencies, like the ability to recognize one's own emotions or those of others, and to manage these emotions effectively in various contexts. Emotional competence can be viewed as the application of emotional abilities in real-world situations, leading to effective behavior and interactions (Vaida & Opre, 2014). By refining this distinction, this study can provide a comprehensive view of the importance of both emotional intelligence and emotional competence in achieving personal and professional success.

Psychological well-being and emotional intelligence, as shaped by theories from Gardner and Sternberg and popularized by Goleman play a critical role in social intelligence. The skills involved - such as recognizing and regulating emotions - are indeed foundational for navigating social interactions. For instance, a teenager who can empathize with peers and read social cues is more likely to establish meaningful connections, boosting their sociometric popularity (acceptance among peers). Conversely, those who leverage emotional intelligence for strategic manipulation might achieve perceived popularity (social dominance), often seen in social hierarchies within schools. Research shows that adolescents with high social intelligence may engage more effectively in group dynamics, leading to greater acceptance by their peers. They might intuitively know when to offer support or when to assert themselves, which can enhance their social standing. This duality of popularity illustrates how emotional and social intelligences intersect with broader social adaptation (Goleman, 2010; Goleman, 2006).

Ultimately, emotional intelligence not only enriches individual relationships but also serves as a powerful predictor of social success, influencing how adolescents navigate complex social landscapes. An interesting study of Silman & Dogan (2013) sheds light on a critical aspect of workplace dynamics among academics, particularly regarding social intelligence and loneliness, enabling a nuanced understanding of how different dimensions of social intelligence influence feelings of loneliness. The finding that social information processing, social skills, and social awareness together account for 26% of social deprivation is significant. It indicates that academics who are adept at interpreting social cues and managing their relationships are less likely to experience feelings of isolation in the workplace. For example, an academic who actively engages with colleagues facilitates collaborative projects, or seeks mentorship may enhance their social network, thereby reducing loneliness (Silman & Dogan, 2013). Additionally, the positive correlation between social skills and social awareness with social companionship suggests that those with strong interpersonal abilities are more likely to cultivate enriching relationships. This could involve initiating informal gatherings or participating in departmental activities, fostering a sense of belonging among peers. Interestingly, the lack of a meaningful explanation from the social information processing sub-dimension regarding social companionship highlights the complexity of social interactions. It suggests that merely processing social information isn't enough to build companionship; actual engagement and skillful interaction are crucial. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of fostering social intelligence in academic settings to combat loneliness, suggesting that training in social skills and awareness could be beneficial for academics aiming to enhance their work environment and personal fulfillment (Devis-Rozental, 2018; Silman & Dogan, 2013; Yao, 2023).

Key factors for developing social intelligence

Social intelligence, which encompasses the skills to navigate social situations effectively, is vital for students' educational development and their ability to bring about progressive change in society. Students' *leadership* strength significantly influences their social intelligence in group settings, enhancing collaboration and problem-solving capabilities. Research indicates that effective leadership fosters better group dynamics and outcomes (Hernández, 2018).

Society recognizes the significance of *humor* in regulating relations between people (Yao, 2023), it is acknowledged as part of social and emotional intelligence (Belessova & Nabi, 2020). The ability to adapt and interact with others is determined by one's humor. It is recognized as a component of optimism, being positively correlated with mental health, level of intelligence, self-esteem, self-acceptance, and sociability (Artemyeva, 2017).

Wisdom, one of the six basic values of humankind, was enormously researched in the previous decennia, and different components of wisdom were elaborated. However, it still has a lot of relevance in today's challenges and needs of society (Vandamme, 2023). In this study perspective or wisdom is seen as the capacity to see the bigger picture and the ability to understand and give advice on life (Bluemke, Partsch, Saucier, & Lechner, 2021). Individuals' level of wisdom determines their life satisfaction (Rezaei & Mousanezhad Jeddi, 2018) and supports their development in different fields. As a society, the level of wisdom determines its prosperity capacity, education being the capstone in wisdom gaining (Ma, Zhu, Li, Zhang, & Tian, 2022).

Enthusiasm seems to be transmissible (Moreno, 2022). Several studies focus on students' enthusiasm for learning (Ma Q., 2022; Tao & Yang, 2023) and teachers' enthusiasm in motivating students' learning (Kim & Schallert, 2014). Students' academic enthusiasm is crucial for their engagement, passion for learning, and success (Ozbakpoor, Karbalaei Harafteh, & Salimi, 2024).

Courage, often perceived as the ability to confront fear, pain, danger, uncertainty, or intimidation, plays a pivotal role in students' personal development and academic achievement (Goleman, Emotional Intelligence, 2010). For students, courage is instrumental in facing academic and social challenges. It is associated with a greater sense of purpose and life satisfaction later in life (Renzulli, 2009). Moreover, courageous adolescents and adults are more likely to actively use coping strategies (Gustems-Carnicer & Calderón, 2015), such as seeking social support and engaging in positive problem-solving (Birden, 2021). In the workplace, courage mediates on quality of life, well-being, and life satisfaction (Mert, Sen, & Alzghol, 2022; Santisi, Lodi, Magnano, Zarbo, & Zammitti, 2000).

The character strength *love of learning* is a positive personality trait that involves a deep and enduring passion for acquiring new knowledge and skills, it is not only about the initial curiosity but also about the ongoing process of learning and the satisfaction derived from it. The love of learning is associated with various positive outcomes in educational and personal contexts, contributing to both academic success and personal well-being (Muhammad Diponegoro & Hanurawan, 2022; Lyons, Lyons, & Jolley, 2019).

The research is progressively acknowledging the implication of character strengths in society. The interdependence between social intelligence and the presented key factors is analyzed in this research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Quantitative data on specific students' personality traits was collected via an online self-report questionnaire. The instrument was developed and made available online in Romanian and English to facilitate foreign student participation. The survey sample consisted of undergraduate and post-graduate students enrolled in the faculty. The questionnaire included demographic variables and 7 personality strength variables: social intelligence, perspective/wisdom, zest/enthusiasm/vitality, leadership, love of learning, humor/playfulness, and valor/bravery/courage. These character strength scales defined based on the study of Bluemke, et al. (2021), were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, each variable being assessed by 4 items. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences program (SPSS) version 29 for Windows.

The study population consisted of 1,671 students enrolled at the Faculty of Business during the 2023-2024 academic year. To ensure the sample was representative of this population, the calculated required sample size was determined to be 313 participants assuming a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level. The study engaged 355 students, surpassing the minimum threshold for statistical representativeness. This high sample coverage strengthens confidence in the reliability and generalizability of the research findings.

Universities stand as a cornerstone in the architecture of social progression, tasked with the critical mission of nurturing the finest human capital. This mission transcends beyond mere preparation for existing market demands, venturing into the realm of fostering social intelligence and behaviors that contribute to a more equitable and sustainable future. In the light of this, the present research report delves into examining the character strengths prevalent among students, with the objective of determining the degree to which these students exhibit the character strengths that support their personal and professional growth in a rapidly changing society.

TABLE 1. Demographic variables

Variable	Items	Percent
Nationality	Romanian	91.83%
	Others	8.17%
Gender:	Masculine	38.87%
	Feminine	60.28%
	Prefer not to say	0.85%
Age	18-25 years	93.52%
	26-35 years	5.07%
	36-45 years	1.13%
	46-55 years	0.28%
Studying year	Bachelor's First year	47.89%
	Bachelor's Second year	30.14%
	Bachelor's Third year	15.49%
	Master's first year	2.82%
	Master's second year	3.66%
Employment	I don't work	67.04%
	I am a full-time employee	10.42%
	I am a part-time employee	13.24%
	I am employed on hourly pay	3.38%
	I am self-employed (freelancer)	5.92%

Source: Authors' calculations.

The sample size for the study is 355 participants. Gender distribution shows a significant skew towards women, who constitute 60.28% of the sample, with men at 38.87% and a marginal 0.85% preferring not to disclose their gender. This gender imbalance could have implications for the generalizability of the study's findings, especially in terms of psychological constructs that may vary across genders. Age-wise, the sample is predominantly young, with 93.52% falling within the 18-25 age bracket. The remaining age groups (26-35 years, 36-45 years, and 46-55 years) are under-represented, which could limit the applicability of the results to a more mature audience.

The overwhelming majority of Romanian nationals in the sample (91.83%) suggest cultural factors may need to be considered when interpreting the data. In terms of educational background, the majority are in their first year of bachelor's degree programs (47.89%), followed by second year (30.14%), third year (15.49%), and master's students (6.48% combined for first and second years). This distribution indicates that the study predominantly reflects the perspectives of undergraduate students in the early stages of higher education. The employment status of the participants shows that a majority (67.04%) are not employed while the others have a full-time job (10.42%), part-time job (13.24%), self-employed (5.92%) or are employed on hourly pay (3.38%) (Table 1).

The descriptive statistic of the character traits variables indicates the highest mean value for playfulness followed by love of learning. The students' enthusiasm encountered the lowest average value (3.5387) and a very near average value had the students' courage (3.5423). The internal consistency of the variables indicates moderate reliability with Cronbach's Alpha coefficient values between 0.49-0.64. These values fall in the same interval as Bluemke et al., 2021 results (Table 2).

TABLE 2. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
Social Intelligence	3.7986	0.69700	0.493	4
Perspective	3.8394	0.70380	0.531	4
Enthusiasm	3.5387	0.77892	0.606	4
Leadership	3.6183	0.79574	0.635	4
Love of Learning	3.9063	0.73540	0.515	4
Playfulness	3.9528	0.76473	0.601	4
Courage	3.5423	0.74431	0.52	4
Valid N (listwise)	355			

Source: Authors' calculations in SPSS.

The bivariate correlations between the variables were measured. The Pearson correlation coefficients between pairs of character traits are reported, with all correlations marked with double asterisks (**) indicating a significant relationship at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). The strength of these correlations ranges from moderate to strong, suggesting that these traits do not exist in isolation. Social intelligence shows significant positive correlations with all the other traits studied. Most notably, social intelligence has a strong correlation with perspective ($r = 0.567^{**}$), indicating that socially intelligent students are likely to have a well-developed ability to understand others' viewpoints. The correlation with leadership ($r = 0.515^{**}$) also stands out, suggesting that socially intelligent students may be more inclined to take on leadership roles, possibly due to their ability to navigate social situations effectively. Leadership, a crucial trait for group dynamics and success, shows significant correlations with all other measured traits. Its strongest correlation is with perspective ($r = .548^{**}$), followed by social intelligence ($r = .515^{**}$), suggesting that effective leaders are those who are both socially aware and able to consider multiple viewpoints. Courage, a trait often associated with risk-taking and resilience, shows a strong correlation with social intelligence ($r = 0.502^{**}$) and moderate correlations with all other traits. Playfulness shows a moderate correlation with all the other traits, with the strongest being with leadership ($r = 0.415^{**}$). This interesting association suggests that a playful attitude may be beneficial in leadership scenarios, possibly by reducing stress and encouraging creative problem-solving. Love of learning demonstrates moderate correlations with all the traits, with the strongest being with perspective ($r = 0.438^{**}$). This may indicate that a love for learning can be associated with a broader view of the world and a deeper understanding of different perspectives.

TABLE 3. Bivariate Correlations

	Social Intelligence	Perspective	Enthusiasm	Leadership	Love of Learning	Playfulness	Courage
Social Intelligence	--						
Perspective	.567**	--					
Enthusiasm	.451**	.360**	--				
Leadership	.515**	.548**	.426**	--			
Love of Learning	.411**	.438**	.366**	.296**	--		
Playfulness	.415**	.368**	.372**	.415**	.304**	--	
Courage	.502**	.430**	.332**	.424**	.333**	.323**	--

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors' calculations in SPSS.

The regression analysis further quantifies these relationships. The multiple linear regression between social intelligence and the group of perspective, enthusiasm, leadership, love of learning, playfulness, and courage indicates an almost strong correlation ($R=0.693<0.7$). The R Square, or coefficient of determination, is 0.48, suggesting that approximately 48% of the variance in social intelligence scores can be explained by the model. When adjusted for the number of predictors, the Adjusted R Square is slightly lower at 0.471, which is expected as it accounts for the degrees of freedom. The ANOVA results confirm the model's significance with an F-value of 53.569 and a p-value less than 0.001. The coefficients reveals that all predictors have a significant positive impact on social intelligence, with perspective having the highest impact. standardized coefficient (Beta = 0.261). The regression signals social intelligence being predicted by the following character traits, in decreasing order. Perspective with a standardized coefficient (Beta = 0.261), being a significant predictor ($p<0.001$), plays an important role in social intelligence. Similarly, courage has a positive effect on social intelligence, with a coefficient of 0.212 ($p < 0.001$). Students who display more courage are likely to have higher social intelligence. The coefficient of 0.15 ($p = 0.001$) indicates that enthusiasm is also a positive predictor, albeit with a slightly lesser impact than perspective and courage. Leadership has a coefficient of 0.146 ($p = 0.004$), denoting its positive association with social intelligence. With a coefficient of 0.105 ($p = 0.019$), playfulness is a significant predictor, but it has a smaller effect size compared to the other traits. Lastly, love of learning has a coefficient of 0.095 ($p = 0.035$), suggesting it is the least strong predictor among those included, but still a significant one. The analysis reveals that perspective and courage are the most influential factors in predicting social intelligence among students (Table 4).

The independent samples test indicates some differences for the measured variables in terms of gender. Levene's Test results show non-significant values for most variables, indicating that the assumption of equal variances holds, allowing the use of the standard t-test for these comparisons. The mean values of variables indicate females scored higher than males except in courage.

TABLE 4. Multiple linear regression

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.693a	0.48	0.471	0.50686		
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	82.572	6	13.762	53.569	<.001b
	Residual	89.402	348	0.257		
	Total	171.974	354			
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.432	0.198		2.187	0.029
	Perspective	0.259	0.05	0.261	5.174	0.000
	Courage	0.198	0.042	0.212	4.673	0.000
	Enthusiasm	0.134	0.041	0.15	3.283	0.001
	Leadership	0.128	0.044	0.146	2.913	0.004
	Playfulness	0.096	0.041	0.105	2.357	0.019
	Love of Learning	0.09	0.043	0.095	2.117	0.035

a. Dependent Variable: Social Intelligence

Source: Authors' calculations in SPSS.

The results show the highest difference in mean values for perspective (-0.27094), followed by love of learning (-0.22294). Statistically, the difference between males and females is confirmed significant (Significance < 0.05) for social intelligence, perspective, leadership, love of learning, and courage. For enthusiasm and playfulness, the difference between males and females is not significant (Significance > 0.05). (Table 5). These findings suggest that gender may play a role in the development or expression of certain psychological traits, implying that educational interventions should address these disparities to promote equality in learning opportunities.

A growing body of research underscores the significance of character strengths in fostering both academic achievement and emotional well-being among students (Gustems & Calderon, 2014). These traits are not only crucial for stimulating positive feelings but also play a pivotal role in enhancing students' performance and success. Several relevant studies' findings underlining the importance of personality traits analyzed in this research are presented as follows.

Playfulness is a positive supporter of social intelligence (Wang, 2024), by using positive humor students can develop better social relationships. Yao's (2023) study on the positive correlation

TABLE 5. Independent Samples Test.

Variables:	Levene's test for equality of variances		t-test for Equality of Means					
	F	Sig.	t	df	Significance		Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
					One-Sided P	Two-Sided P		
[Male: 138] [Female: 214]								
Social Intelligence	0.056	0.813	-2.348	350	0.010	0.019	-0.17701	0.07540
Perspective	0.054	0.817	-3.621	350	0.000	0.000	-0.27094	0.07483
Enthusiasm	0.889	0.346	-0.242	350	0.404	0.809	-0.02049	0.08456
Leadership	0.000	0.984	-1.997	350	0.023	0.047	-0.17178	0.08602
Love of Learning	0.024	0.878	-2.813	350	0.003	0.005	-0.22294	0.07925
Playfulness	0.365	0.546	-0.610	350	0.271	0.543	-0.05103	0.08371
Courage	0.797	0.373	2.378	350	0.009	0.018	0.19201	0.08074

Source: Authors' calculations in SPSS.

between humor and interpersonal relationships of students confirmed this hypothesis. The role of humor has also proved to be important in emergencies (Belessova & Nabi, 2020). The humor in a group influences its status quo, it is part of the communicative process within the group (Lynch, 2010). Humor can be used positively or negatively by teachers. One study on students' perceptions of lecturer humor styles confirmed the positive impact of affiliative humor on students' perceptions and the negative effect of aggressive humor (James & Fox, 2024). Another study proved the mediating role of humor on social intelligence and interpersonal problems finding a positive relation between emotional clarity and affiliative and self-enhancing humor types, while interpersonal problems were negatively correlated with these humor styles, recognising the position of humor in emotional repair (유금란 & 강수정, 2016). Another study underscores the prevalent role of humor as a socially adaptive mechanism utilized by students. The students' self-reported beliefs regarding the relational and stress-relieving functions of humor point to the potential psychosocial benefits associated with humor. Students with high levels of humor revealed proper self-esteem and self-control (Artemyeva, 2017).

Wisdom or perspective could be perceived as emotional and social intelligence in practice (Boyatzis, 2007). The students' perspective level directly determines their social intelligence (Ma, Zhu, Li, Zhang, & Tian, 2022) and further the life satisfaction (Rezaei & Mousanezhad Jeddi, 2018). Wisdom was seen as one of the society pillars decades ago, in the Grec, Mesopotamian, Indian, Chinese, Islamic, and Roman cultures (Vandamme, 2023).

Students' enthusiasm plays a critical role in shaping their social intelligence and overall educational experience. A study on college students in China mentions the degree of socialist core values education enthusiasm received by students, underlining the importance of creating a good atmosphere (Ma Q., 2022). One study focused on the students' hold and catch interest in a course being affiliated with teachers' enthusiasm and peers' enthusiasm (Kim & Schallert, 2014). As enthusiasm can be contagious, teachers should consider promoting it (Moreno, 2022). One study identified the factors of low enthusiasm of students, indicating teachers' demands and parents' requirements

impact their learning enthusiasm (Gao & Fu, 2017). Academic enthusiasm has a mediating role between the moral and social atmosphere of the class and students' self-efficacy (Ali Sami Qasim Al-Obeidi, Mohajeran, & Hasani, 2024). Another study emphasizes the importance of cultivating an educational environment that effectively supports self-efficacy, finally giving rise to increased enthusiasm and vitality (Luo, Ahmadi, & Izadpanah, 2024).

Love of learning drives individuals to seek out new knowledge, explore innovative ideas, and adapt to changing circumstances (Lyons, Lyons, & Jolley, 2019). A student with a strong love of learning is inherently curious and driven to explore new concepts, which naturally leads to higher engagement and academic achievement. Similarly, social intelligence allows students to navigate social situations effectively, fostering positive relationships that can translate into collaborative learning opportunities and a supportive learning environment (Weber, Wagner, & Ruch, 2016). A study found that students with higher social intelligence demonstrated better understanding and engagement in social sciences, indicating a direct link between social skills and academic success (Moshahid & Quraishi, 2022). Social intelligence has been positively correlated with academic performance, suggesting that students who engage socially tend to achieve higher results. Engaging in academic activities promotes interpersonal intelligence, as students learn to navigate social dynamics and improve their communication skills (El-Yunusi, Abu Bakar, & Mardiyah, 2022).

The development of leadership character strength in students is closely linked to enhanced social intelligence and improved academic performance. Research indicates that leadership ability significantly influences students' academic achievements and their ability to collaborate effectively with peers (Repuela, De Los Santos, Viking, & Polinar, 2024). Students exhibiting strong leadership qualities demonstrate higher levels of collaboration and positive interactions within their groups (Hernandez, 2018). The development of leadership character traits in students can enhance social intelligence, leading to improved academic performance, as highlighted in the research on diaspora students' social intelligence (Dyussenova et al., 2023).

Courage is correlated with psychological empowerment, it is a facilitator of social engagement (Santisi, Lodi, Magnano, Zarbo, & Zammitti, 2000). Courageous students are better equipped to manage social fears and engage more fully in their social environments (Mert, Sen, & Alzghol, 2022). Courage, optimism, and vision determine the students' social intelligence (Renzulli, 2009). In the social-emotional learning curricula, courage is one of the elements considered. This underlines the importance of nurturing both courage and social intelligence to foster a classroom culture where students feel safe, nurtured, connected, and empowered (Birden, 2021). The importance of zest, love of learning, perseverance, and social intelligence were confirmed as predictors of students' success (Weber, Wagner, & Ruch, 2016). Emotions can significantly influence teacher-student interactions, which can catalyze the teaching-learning process, while curiosity and humor can develop socio-emotional intelligence (Devis-Rozental, 2018). A person's socio-emotional competencies can play a pivotal role in the attainment of their personal goals or the failure to achieve them (Goleman, 2010).

CONCLUSIONS

Contrary to the common misconception that character strengths are innate, research suggests they are malleable traits that can be cultivated and strengthened through deliberate practice and intentional development (Lyons, Lyons, & Jolley, 2019; Štrukelj, Zlatanović, Nikolić, & Zabukovšek, 2019). Individuals are born with a natural inclination toward curiosity (Raine & Pandya, 2019),

which serves as a foundational element for the love of learning (Bayar, Sart, Gavriletea, & Coroş, 2022; van der Westhuizen, 2023), Students cultivating virtues such as perspective, enthusiasm, leadership, courage, love of learning, and playfulness are better equipped to cope with stress and adversity, enhancing their personal growth and adaptation to challenging situations. The research is increasingly recognizing the importance of character strengths such as zest, love of learning, perseverance, and social intelligence in students' academic achievement and emotional well-being. These traits are not only crucial for fostering positive feelings but also play a pivotal role in enhancing students' performance (Weber, Wagner, & Ruch, 2016).

Socio-emotional intelligence is a vital aspect of human functioning that encompasses the skills necessary for managing emotions and navigating social interactions. Its importance cannot be overstated, as it impacts not only individual well-being, health (Zeidner, Matthews, & Roberts, 2011) but also the dynamics within groups and organizations. As society continues to recognize the value of these skills, the cultivation of socio-emotional intelligence will likely become an increasingly important goal for educational and professional development programs. Encouraging social intelligence in students may lead them to learn to strengthen themselves, stay focused, and perform well without being disrupted by emotions (Fato, 2024). Students' ability to manage their emotions and social dimensions is key to their well-being, happiness, and empowerment. Emotional and social intelligence are integral components of learning communities, where students can thrive in an environment that supports personal progression and positive socialization. Additionally, social and emotional competencies are critical for students' development and are closely linked to student engagement and overall well-being (Gustems & Calderon, 2014).

This study underlined the significance of social intelligence and supportive personality traits in fostering positive behavior. By understanding and cultivating these traits, individuals can better adapt to their environment and promote harmonious societal relationships. The correlation between measured character traits and social intelligence is a substantial finding that has practical implications for educational institutions. Universities should consider integrating social intelligence development into their curricula and support services to foster students' interpersonal relationships and collective well-being. By strategic incorporation of humor-based interventions, leadership supports courage reinforcements, love of learning stimulations, perspective developments, and enthusiastically implicating students, the education body will enforce more sustainable education and society.

The gender differences observed suggest that educational interventions may need to be tailored to address the specific needs and strengths of male and female students. Moreover, the cultural homogeneity of the sample indicates that further research with a more diverse population is necessary to understand the universality of these findings. Future research should aim to address the limitations of this study, such as the underrepresentation of certain demographics, to ensure a more comprehensive understanding of student personality traits across diverse populations.

This research has some limitations. Focusing mainly on perspective, love of learning, leadership, courage, enthusiasm, humor, and leadership, there may be other factors influencing social intelligence, as the results indicate. The generalizability of the results is limited due to the nationality of respondents. Replication studies in different countries and universities improve the ability to generalize the outcomes to diverse cultures and contexts.

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the need for educational institutions to cultivate character traits in students, despite the studying field, suggesting that personality development is a synergistic

process. These insights could be instrumental in shaping educational practices and student support services, ultimately contributing to the development of young individuals. The implications of these findings could be far-reaching, impacting educational strategies, leadership training, and personal development programs. Educational institutions and psychologists might consider these findings when developing curricula and interventions to foster well-being and social values among students.

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